

Experimental investigation on mechanical behaviors of novel hybrid structure of composite to metal

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ABSTRACT

In order to improve the mechanical properties of the metal-composite hybrid joints, we developed a new joint method, which is called adhesive-multi pin joint method. Both the adhesive between the metallic and composite substrates and some very thin metallic pins running through the substrates in the overlap area transfer the load in this new joint. Metal-composite joints made by traditional adhesive bonded method and new joint method were tensile tested for comparison. The results demonstrated that the proposed joint method can improve the failure load, failure strain, and energy absorption capacity significantly, in addition to that, it can decrease the suddenness of the failure of the joint. All these indications of damage occurring to a joint could promote detection of a problem in a structure before the catastrophic failure. Through the analysis of the failure process of the two different joints, it can be concluded that there is bridging force between the pins so that the pin not only inhibits the peeling of the adhesive layer and the laminate, also transfer load between the joint plates together with the adhesive layer.

Keywords: Adhesive-multi pin joints; Composite-to-metal; Manufacturing; Tensile testing; Mechanical behaviors

1 INTRODUCTION

Reliable and efficient joint technology between metallic and FRP parts is important to improve the use of the composite materials. Both adhesive bonding and mechanical fastening have their advantages and drawbacks. Adhesive bonding has high load transfer efficiency, however, the failure of adhesively bonded joints occurs unexpectedly and abruptly due to the high stress concentration at the ends of adhesive joints [1]. Therefore, the adhesive joints cannot meet the requirements of damage tolerance in transport category airplanes. Mechanical fastening technology is more reliable than bonding, but the strength reduction due to these holes for composite structures is much greater than that of metals because of the high notch sensitivity of composite laminates [2]. In addition to that, the use of a large number of fasteners leads to the high cost and brings an increase in structural weight as well. This may weaken the reduction of structural weight which benefits from the use of composite materials.

The adhesive-bolts hybrid joint method overcomes some shortcomings of two afore-mentioned methods. However, the use of fasteners increases the cost and weight of the structure and, to a certain extent, weakens the benefits of using composite materials. Comeld [3-7] is a new technology which is used to produce joints between fibers reinforced plastic (FRP) composite materials and metals by pre-treating the metallic joint component using Surf-Sculpt™ technology which is recently developed by TWI. Mouring et al. [8] of the US Naval Academy investigated the load carrying capacity of Comeld™ structures and they found that this new improved the carrying capacity based on the traditional adhesive joint. Furthermore, this technology is only suitable for uncured composites, metal pin cannot be embedded in the cured composite plate. It will occur a certain degree of limitations in practical application.

A new metal-composite joint method will be developed and its reliability and structural efficiency will be evaluated through comparative tests of traditional adhesive joints.

2 SPECIMEN DESCRIPTION

A typical composite to metal adhesive-multi pin single lap joint which designed refer to ASTM D 1002-10 standard [9] is shown in Figure 1. The adhesive-multi pin joint is integrated with adhesion which bonds the faying surface of two plates, and an array of pins (the diameter is about 1 mm) which run through holes and distribute in the overlap region. In Figure 1, s is the row distance and p is the column distance of the pins.

The composite plate is made of carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminate with 0.188 mm nominal ply thickness and the laminate's stacking sequence is $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$. The material of the metallic plate and pin is 45# steel. Material properties of unidirectional fiber composite is listed in Table 1. Dimensions of both plates are 100 mm \times 25 mm \times 12 mm in length, width and thickness. The adhesive used to bond the metallic pin with the adherends is HY-914 and that between the two adherends is Hysol EA9696.

Figure 1: Specimen geometry configuration (all dimensions in mm) .

Engineering constant		Value
E_{11}	[GPa]	121
E_{22}	[GPa]	9.9
ν_{12}	—	0.3
G_{12}	[GPa]	3.6

Table 1: Mechanical properties of unidirectional fiber composite

The manufacture of adhesive-multi pin joint was carried out according to the following procedure. Firstly, surface treatment was implemented on the overlap of the metal parts and the cured composite parts. Bond the surface as soon after preparation as possible. The procedures of surface treatment were in accordance with ASTM D 2093 standard [10]. The treated overlap area of the metal parts and the composite parts were bonded by adhesive layer, so that metal parts and composite materials achieve the pre-positioning through the adhesive layer. Then drill an array of holes ($\varphi=1$ mm) in overlap area using positioning punch fixture. The array of hole ran through the composite plate and the metal plate at the same time. After that, the adhesive was uniformly applied to the pin surface, and then the pins with the adhesive were inserted into the array of holes. Before this procedure, the same surface treatment as overlap area was implemented on the metal pins. Finally, the adhesive-multi pin joint were placed in the metal mold. The adhesive were cured with pressure in the 120°C environment for an hour, and then the

temperature naturally dropped to room temperature. For comparison, adhesive bonded specimens with equal geometry as the newly proposed hybrid specimen were chosen as a reference and the same procedure is implemented. The adhesive and adhesive-multi pin single lap joints are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Single lap joints

3 EXPERIMENTAL TEST

Tensile tests were conducted on a universal testing machine of type CMT 5105 with a load range from 0 to 100 kN in accordance with ASTM D 1002-10 standard [9]. Reaction force was recorded with a tolerance of $\pm 1\%$. Specimens were clamped vertically with the metallic plate downward and the composite plate upward (Figure 3). The specimens were placed in the grips of the testing machine and outer 25 mm of each end were in contact with the jaws, so that the long axis of the test specimen coincided with the direction of applied load through the center line of the grip assembly. Before the specimens were clamped, pads were attached at both ends of the specimens. The thickness of pad at the metallic plate end was the same as the thickness of composite plate and that at the composite end was the same as the thickness of metallic plate. The experiment was displacement-controlled with a free crosshead velocity of 0.2 mm/min. Data for both global and local system was recorded with a frequency of 5 Hz.

Figure 3: Tension test

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Load vs. displacement curve of joints

Two different types of specimens were tensile tested. The load–displacement relationships of three specimens in each type of test have good consistency. A typical experimental results is shown in Figure 4. The load vs displacement curves demonstrate that adhesive-multi pin joints have a significantly greater load carrying capability than adhesive joints. The area under the load–displacement curves represents the energy absorbed during failure of the specimens. For both types of joints, the energy absorbed by adhesive-multi pin joint is more than four times that absorbed by the adhesive joint. Moreover, adhesive joint fails at the bond line and these failures are very catastrophic, as indicated by the sharp change in slope of the corresponding curves.

An important fact to note is that failure of the adhesive-multi pin joint is more progressive than the abrupt failure of the traditional adhesive joint. The load-displacement curves of adhesive-multi pin joint exhibit greater changes in slope than that of the adhesive joints. In addition, the drop-off of load which represents the final failure appears much later. In the case of the single lap specimens, as shown in Figure 4, the joint retained an amount of load carrying capability for a long time after the initial drop in load. This promotes the detection of defects in a structure before sudden failure occurred.

Figure 4: Comparison of load-displacement curves between adhesive joint and adhesive-multi pin joint.

4.2 Failure mode of joints

The two types of joints have different failure mode, as shown in Figure 5. Adhesive joint is damaged under the action of the shearing force and adhesion between the metal plate and the composite plate takes place cohesive destruction. There was very little damage to the metal or composite parts. As for adhesive-multi pin joint, adhesion did not fail at low loads, the composite material occurred damage when loads reached its failure strength. Damage was visible before failure caused by matrix cracking, whereas adhesive occurred failure abruptly. The composite material is destroyed in the direction of 45° layer. It also can be seen that the angle of some metal pins change significantly before and after joint breaking. Some metal pins occurred plastic deformation and evenly occurred fracture failure. The adhesive-multi pin joint eventually failed due to fracture failure of metal pins and shear failure of the composite, which contributed to different mechanical behaviors. Therefore, it can be considered that the improvement of mechanical behaviors between the composite part and the metal part mainly because pin not only inhibits the peeling of the adhesive layer, but also pass the load between the connected parts together with the adhesive layer.

(a) Adhesive joints

(b) Adhesive-multi pin joints

Figure 5: Status of jointing points between metal and composite after joint breaking

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, an adhesive-multi pin metal-composite structure, which reinforced with adhesion and metal pins, is presented to enhance the performance of hybrid metal-composite single lap joints. Adhesive joints and adhesive-multi pin joints were tested under tensile loading for comparison. Finite element model were proposed for numerical investigation. Based on experimental and numerical results, the conclusions can be obtained as follow:

1) Comparing with adhesive joint, the joint reinforced by metal pin show improvements in ultimate failure load, failure strain and energy absorption capacity. These excellent properties make the applicability of the adhesive-multi pin joint wider than adhesive joint.

2) There is bridging force between the pin passing through the connecting part and the connected part so that the pin not only inhibits the peeling of the adhesive layer and the laminate, but also pass the load between the connected parts together with the adhesive layer.

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